

Optimised geometries in real conditions for the characterisation of photometric quantities for road surface materials

EMPIR GRANT Agreement 16NRM02 SURFACE

Draft 1.4

V. Muzet - Cerema

P. Iacomussi - INRIM

F. Manoocheri – AALTO

A. Jouanin – OPTIS ANSYS

T. Kubarsepp - METROSERT

D2 deliverable of the EMPIR Joint Research Project

16NRM02 SURFACE

Title : OPTIMISED GEOMETRIES IN REAL CONDITIONS FOR THE CHARACTERISATION OF PHOTOMETRIC QUANTITIES FOR ROAD SURFACE MATERIALS

Reference : EMPIR 16NRM02

Version : 1.4

Date : 27-04-2020

Dissemination level : PUBLIC **EMBARGO UP TO December 2020**

Author(s) : **AALTO**
Cerema
INRIM
METROSERT
OPTIS ANSYS

Keywords : Luminance coefficient, Geometries, Measurement condition, Lighting pollution, r-tables

Abstract : Specification concerning road lighting and the photometry of road surface was established more than 40 years ago. Road lighting design and characterisation of marking visibility have been developed for car driving. The observation distance defined by standards corresponds to inter urban applications, where in Europe there is no or little use of road lighting.. The objective of the EMPIR Surface project is to propose new geometries for the photometric characterization of pavements, both adapted to different urban travel modes and new lighting technologies. The first part of this document is a review on available guidelines, standards and literature regarding geometries and road lighting applications. The second part presents the project EMPIR SURFACE analysis and proposal. Based on standards and bibliography, the Surface consortium proposed angles for different driving conditions and road users: for urban environment 2,29°, for extra-urban environment 1° (and for consistency with previous geometries). The angle of 5° corresponding to 17 m viewing distance could be an interesting compromise, suitable for urban driving at low speed, cycling and for scooters. Two different proposals (10° and 20°) are also under consideration for describing the boundary between the diffusing and specular behaviour.

Contact : <https://surface-nrm02.eu>

About the EMPIR

The European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) coordinates research projects to address grand challenges, while supporting and developing the SI system of measurement units. There is an increased focus within EMPIR on innovation activities to target the needs of industry and accelerate the uptake of research outputs. The programmes capacity-building projects aim to bridge the gap between EU member states with emerging measurement systems and those with more developed capabilities. The EMPIR is jointly supported by the European Commission and the participating countries within the European Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET e.V.). The EMPIR will ensure collaboration between National Measurement Institute, reducing duplication and increasing impact. The overall goal of the EMPIR is to accelerate innovation and competitiveness in Europe whilst continuing to provide essential support to underpin the quality of our lives.

See <https://msu.euramet.org> for more information

About the 16NRM02 SURFACE

SURFACE aims at providing metrological foundations for the photometric characterisation of road surfaces in order to realise lighting systems, such as smart and adaptative lighting systems. The project is a Joint Research Project coordinated by INRiM, belonging to the European Metrology

16 NRM SURFACE
Version 1.3

*Research Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) of the European Metrology Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET).
See <https://surface-nrm02.eu> for more information*

SUMMARY

Specification concerning road lighting and the photometry of road surface was established more than 40 years ago. Road lighting design and characterisation of marking visibility have been developed for car driving. The observation distance defined by standards corresponds to inter urban applications, where there is where in Europe there is no or little use of road lighting. The objective of the EMPIR SURFACE project is to propose new geometries for the photometric characterization of pavements, both adapted to different urban travel modes and new lighting technologies. The first part of this document is a review on available guidelines, standards and literature regarding geometries and road lighting applications. The second part presents the project EMPIR SURFACE analysis and proposal. Based on standards and bibliography, the SURFACE consortium proposed angles for different driving conditions and road users: for urban environment $2,29^\circ$, for extra-urban environment 1° (and for consistency with previous geometries). The angle of 5° corresponding to 17m viewing distance could be an interesting compromise, suitable for urban driving at low speed, cycling and for scooters. Two different proposals (10° and 20°) are also under consideration for describing the boundary between diffusing and specular behaviour.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	REVIEW OF GUIDELINES AND STANDARDS REGARDING GEOMETRY	3
1.1	Pavement photometry	3
1.2	ROAD MARKING PHOTOMETRY	5
2	LITERATURE REVIEW REGARDING GEOMETRY	6
3	EMPIR SURFACE ANALYSIS	10
3.1	Illumination angles	10
3.2	Observation angle	10
4	CONCLUSIONS	12
5	REFERENCES	14

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 : a. The photometric characteristics of the road surface depend on the angles of observation α , sight β and incidence γ . O represents the eye of the driver and P the point of observation. By convention according to CIE 66 and CIE 144 guidelines and road lighting standards, for the characterisation of road photometry, α is set at 1° . b. Boundaries of sight angle β and incidence angle γ defined in CIE144³ and representation of the integration surface for the calculation of the brightness coefficient Q_03

Figure 2 : Defined geometry for the photometric characterisation of marking according to the standard⁵. a. Retroreflection factor R_L , b. Day visibility factor Q_d5

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Stopping distance at different driving speed 10

Table 2: corresponding distance for different observation angles..... 11

INTRODUCTION

Specification concerning road lighting and the photometry of road surface was established more than 40 years ago. Road lighting design and characterisation of marking visibility have been developed for car driving. The observation distance defined by standards corresponds to inter urban applications, where there is where in Europe there is nearly no or little use of road lighting. The objective of the EMPIR SURFACE project is to propose new geometries for the photometric characterization of pavements, both adapted to different urban travel modes and new lighting technologies. The first part of this document is a review on available guidelines, standards and literature regarding geometries and road lighting applications. The second part presents the project EMPIR SURFACE analysis and proposal.

1 REVIEW OF GUIDELINES AND STANDARDS REGARDING GEOMETRY

1.1 Pavement photometry

The methodology of characterisation of pavement photometry was developed in the seventies and eighties¹. Road surface reflection properties are given in a reduced coefficient table, where the luminance coefficient q are given as a combination of fixed lighting angles β and $\tan \gamma$ (see Figure 1a). The standardised viewing height is 1.5m and the angle of observation α is constant at 1° corresponding to an observation distance of 86m. The lighting standards use the area of the road between 60m and 160m ahead of the driver, because it is considered an important area for the detection of obstacles.

Figure 1 : a. The photometric characteristics of the road surface depend on the angles of observation α , sight β and incidence γ . O represents the eye of the driver and P the point of observation. By convention according to CIE 66 and CIE 144 guidelines and road lighting standards, for the characterisation of road photometry, α is set at 1° . b. Boundaries of sight angle β and incidence angle γ defined in CIE1443 and representation of the integration surface for the calculation of the brightness coefficient Q_0 .

The r-table is a two-dimensional table with a number of standardized combinations of the incidence lighting angle γ and orientation angle β , the boundaries of which define the solid angle Ω . The illumination angles are between 0° and 180° for β and between 0 and 12 for $\tan(\gamma)$ with some missing combinations for the grazing angles. But when the mounting height of luminaires is very low ($H < 2$ m), an extended format in $\tan(\gamma)$ is needed. In that case, the distance from the luminaires to certain points of the calculation grid is greater than $5H$ or even $12H$ and the standard table cannot be used so that luminance at these points cannot be evaluated. In EN13201-34, there is an informative annex B that defines an extended r-table format for low mounting height luminaire. The r-table is extended in $\tan \gamma$ up to 20 by 0.5 increment for every β angle (the number

16 NRM SURFACE
Version 1.3

and values of β angles remain the same as usual). No updated calculation of the brightness coefficient is proposed in the standard.

1.2 ROAD MARKING PHOTOMETRY

Concerning the characterization of road marking, other geometries are defined in the standard EN1436¹⁴. The eye of the observer is set at 1.2m and the angle of observation is 2.29° , which makes a distance of observation of 30m. The retroreflection factor R_L corresponds to the night visibility of the marking, with an illumination angle of 1.24° . The day visibility Q_d is the quotient of reflected luminance at 2.29° under a diffuse illumination.

Figure 2 : Defined geometry for the photometric characterisation of marking according to the standard 5. a. Retroreflection factor R_L , b. Day visibility factor Q_d .

2 LITERATURE REVIEW REGARDING GEOMETRY

In the nineties, Sorensen⁶ suggested to use Q_d instead of Q_0 for road lighting specification. Both were measured at an observation angle of 1° at that time. A methodology of computation of Q_d with an r-table is given. A device able to measure Q_d and Q_0 was developed⁶ with an observation angle of 1.37° corresponding to a height of 1.2m and a distance of 50m. Sorensen compared⁷ the calculation of $L_{average}/E_{average}$ done for the standard r-tables defined in 1 to the values of Q_d and Q_0 . For the road lighting installation used, Q_d gave the best estimate of the average luminance. In a 1997 French study⁹, the same calculation of L/E was done with 12 lighting installation and 164 pavements. The measured r-tables were used for the calculation of L/E and the computation of Q_0 and Q_d . The results obtained are always better with the use of Q_0 . The Q_d factor underestimates the specular effect and the differences are bigger for the grazing angles. After all these works, the CIE 144 publication³ confirmed the observation angle of 1° and the use of Q_0 for the pavement characterisation and an observation angle of 2.29° for roadmarking.

In Gibbons 1997 PhD study¹⁰, a 4 angle gonioreflectometer was used and the influence of different observation angle was studied on 20 cores of pavements with $\alpha=1^\circ, 2^\circ, 3^\circ, 5^\circ, 7^\circ, 10^\circ, 12^\circ, 15^\circ, 20^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 90° and has shown that the pavement lightness changes with the observation angle and that except for the smaller observation angles, the specularity decreases with the observation angles.

Figure 3: Influence of the observation angle on Q_0 (a) and S_1 (b).

In the more recent literature, different proposals of observation angles were done by Chain¹¹: 90° for the characterisation of light from planes, 3° for urban application, 10° for cyclist and pedestrians and 45° for visually impaired people. Some oculometric studies^{12,13} show differences in visual strategy of cyclists as a

function of age, but none of them proposes a preponderant angle of observation. This aspect is not addressed in Fotios recent review¹⁴.

Stockmar¹⁵ also proposed an angle of 3°, more adapted to urban applications. In his study, he indicates that the use of an observation angle of 3° instead of 1° induces a 10% reduction of Q₀. Sorensen¹⁶ has developed a device able to measure at 1°, 1.5° and 2.29°. The first results on two pavements show that the impact on Q₀ and S₁ is weak especially for Q₀ (and Q_d). The specularity factor S₁ drops with the increasing angle.

In Greffier case study²⁵, the impact of using observation angles of 2.29°, 3° and 5° was studied with a mobile ILMD. The luminance and uniformities were calculated according to EN13201 mesh grid with concept of a mobile observer proposed by Stockmar¹⁵. The first results show that the luminance decreases with the increase of the observation angle.

Figure 4 : a. Example of a luminance image taken with CYCLOPE ILMD. The areas corresponding to the different angles of observation are represented in red for 1°, in green for 2.29°, in blue for 3° and pink for 5°. b. Corresponding luminance measured between two lamps with the concept of a moving observer for the same observation angles.

For visually impaired people, the observation angle is set at 45° in the standard concerning pedotactile caution warning devices²⁴. The eye of the observer is also set by convention at 1.5m.

For obtrusive light, the angle depends on the geometrical position of the observer and there is no standardised rule²² (CIE 150:2017). Concerning the impact of light pollution on astronomical observation, no specific angle is given, but the largest impact of light is the one radiated in direction close to the horizon (mainly 90-110° i.e. 0 to 20° from the horizon). In Soardo paper¹⁷, the same lighting grazing angles are also the major problem because of the diffusion in the atmosphere. On the other hand, the use of optics reducing all the spill light could have some drawbacks because to comply with standard specification, the amount of light could be more important. Grazing lighting angles and direct light onto the road up to 70-75° give the best lighting efficiency for luminaires equipped with glass bowls (because of the boundary between the refractive index of air and the one of glass), but bowls luminaires have a little upward light (about 2- 3%).

However, simulation has shown that using such luminaires generate less light pollution for astronomers because the amount of emitted light is less important.

It is to note that lighting pollution and energy consumption are clearly related to illuminance on the road¹⁸, while visibility and safety are directly linked to luminance measured along the observation direction (namely in current standard 1°). The advantages of using an observation direction close to the actual need of road-users, as in the SURFACE proposal on geometry for pavements characterization, is obvious.

According to the experience of the astronomers¹⁹⁻²¹, the artificial sky luminance is mainly generated by the luminous flux, both emitted directly by the luminaires and reflected by the illuminated surfaces, within the range of elevation between 0° and 20° over the horizontal plane. At such elevations, the light crosses the low levels of the atmosphere, where the veiling luminance generated by the downward diffusion of the aerosol into the entrance pupil of a telescope. This reduces the contrast of the heavenly bodies since it adds to the natural sky luminance. The upward light with elevations higher than 20° crosses higher layers of the atmosphere, where aerosols are not present, generating a much lower downward diffusion due to the molecules. The same approach can be extended to the road surface for extra-urban application. For urban application, based on the theoretical model of light pollution town behaviour^{19,17, 21} the town can be assimilated to a single uniformly diffusing source, because most luminaires are hidden into the cavities between the buildings and few luminaires are not screened by buildings (typical on the boundary of the town or of large empty area)

Figure 5: A single scheme for all the light components which generate the artificial sky luminance.

Figure 6: The downward diffusion due to aerosol and molecules in the atmosphere

The only way for improving the astronomic observations is to reduce the prescription of road luminance, for zones close to the observatories, ensuring the safety of road users through alternative subsidiary means. This can be achieved with higher lighting levels at the intersections and on the pedestrian crossings, while moreover calling the attention of the drivers with conspicuous internally illuminated signs. In some cases, for example when conflict traffic does not exist like in the highways, this strategy could replace completely the lighting installations, with a considerable advantage in foggy weather because of the absence of the veiling luminance generated by the luminaires.

In calculation of obtrusive light and in particular for the calculation of the upward flux ratio²², the reflectance of the road is a ratio between the incident illuminance and the reflected illuminance measured in one meter height²³. It should be mentioned that the given examples of different surface reflectance are based on measurements done in the nineties and have not been updated till then.

3 EMPIR SURFACE ANALYSIS

3.1 Illumination angles

Concerning the illumination angles, there is a need of more grazing angles due to the use of guiding lighting devices at low heights, especially in tunnels. This is why an extended table was proposed in EN13201-34 (annex B). It is an extension in $\tan(\gamma)$ up to 20 by 0.5 increment for every β angle. There is still a need for such data and a new calculation of Q_0 should be proposed to take into account this table. However, up to now, it seems that nobody is able to make measurements at such grazing angles. So despite the proposal of this table in the standard, no data are available, and no commercial instruments are able to perform the measurements.

3.2 Observation angle

For drivers of motorized vehicles, in the EN13201 standard, the main lighting criteria for interurban driving are based on the road surface luminance and include the average luminance, the overall uniformity and the longitudinal uniformity. The driver's eye is assumed at 1.5 m above the road surface and the angle of observation is fixed to 1° below the horizontal, corresponding to a distance of 86 m ahead of the observer. This geometry is well adapted for a speed of 90 km/h, on motorways for example. But nowadays, except in tunnels, there is not a lot of interurban lighted roads among Europe. Illuminated areas are located in urban environments where there are several types of users on the road (drivers but also cyclers or pedestrians) having different circulation speeds. To define new observation angles, a first approach is to consider the stopping distance, which is a summation of the distance travelled in the reaction time and the breaking distance. Typical stopping distances are presented in the Table 1. For road safety, good visibility of obstacles at stopping distance is very important. The CIE defined observation angle of 1° is adapted for a good visibility at a distance of 86m that corresponds to an interurban driving at about 90km/h. In urban environment, it is necessary to define other observation angles adapted to a stopping distance that corresponds to the urban driving speeds.

Table 1: Stopping distance at different driving speed

	SPEED	Dry pavement	Wet pavement
Urban driving	20km/h	8m	9m
	30km/h	13m	14m
	50km/h	27m	34m

Inter urban driving	90km/h	68m	89m
	120km/h	108m	144m

Concerning the height of the observer, SURFACE proposal is to keep the height of the observer at 1.5m to be consistent with EN13201 and CIE recommendation. This height can also be used for drivers, cyclers and pedestrians. In the Table 2, the corresponding distance is computed for different observation angles.

Table 2: corresponding distance for different observation angles

Observation angle α (°)	1	2,29	3	5	7	10	20	45
Corresponding distance (m)	85,9	37,5	28,6	17,1	12,2	8,5	4,1	1,5

Based on standards and bibliography, the SURFACE consortium proposed angles²⁷ for different driving conditions and road users: for urban environment 2,29°, for extra-urban environment 1° (and for consistency with previous geometries). The angle of 5° corresponding to 17m viewing distance could be an interesting compromise, suitable for urban driving at low speed, cycling and for scooters. Two different proposals (10° and 20°) are also under consideration for describing the boundary diffusing-specular behaviour. Light pollution studies highlighted the relevance of reflected light up to 20°, while above road surfaces have a typical Lambertian behaviour.

4 CONCLUSIONS

SURFACE project has been able, during its duration, to produce an extensive international review on road photometry, including measurement devices, available data base, measurement methods, national choices of reference values for lighting design and energetic impact²⁸, but not only. SURFACE investigated also current geometries for road surface characterization and road-users conditions of viewing, and is able to suggest to international normative bodies (CEN and CIE) these findings and new approaches.

Regarding geometries the first evidence is about the most critical point of the current approach: the reference observation angle currently used in standard. The difficulties of doing measurements at 1° observation angle were already recognized in literature, but SURFACE not only highlighted and substantiated these issues but also proposed solutions. The large literature review and investigation among the SURFACE consortium and stakeholders whose results are summarized in this report bring SURFACE to suggest to reference normative bodies (CIE and CEN) the use of different geometries according the actual road environment, branching out several possible observation angles to be included at the earliest review stage of CIE 144 and EN 13201 documents.

Road environment condition	Observation angle suggestion
Extra-urban road	1°, viewing distance of 85,9 m
Urban road	2,29°, viewing distance of 37,5 m

SURFACE suggests additional observation angles of 5°, 10° and 20° more suitable for specific applications like, pedestrian area (2,29° and 5°) or light pollution impact evaluation (10°, 20°) for which the investigations are ongoing. During the project intercomparison tests, measurements are conducted at 1°, 2.29°, 10° and 20°.

The impact of the above new geometries for road surface characterization needs to be verified by lighting design programs and simulation tools, too. If some measurement devices for road luminance coefficient evaluation, can be easily adapted to the new angles of observation and other are going to be introduced in the market (two of them have been developed inside the SURFACE consortium), it is to relevant to highlight that the same geometries have to be used also in lighting design and on-site verification too: the coherence

between viewing conditions in road characterization (and reference tables), in lighting design and in on-site verifications, need to be assured.

Furthermore, these new geometries, allow the development of less expensive measurement devices and an increased accuracy also for on-site verification: geometrical constraints of 1° of observation entail difficulties in set up, increase influence of discrepancies in alignments and of lighting – viewing area, as well for on site verification, the identification of measurement grid points and associated luminance values.

The findings of SURFACE have impacts also on the energy consumption: SURFACE already highlighted the advantages of using bright pavements and smart-lighting²⁸.

Additional impacts are expected also on luminance levels required for the different road lighting class: the current reference values are based on the results of visual experiments, carried out in the past century more than 60 years ago, on contrast threshold at 1° of observation angle on pavements and lit road of that period.

The definition of new angles of observation would have an impact on the required threshold luminance levels of uniformity. New subjective experiments are needed in order to define new reference values of contrast threshold to acknowledge not only the new SURFACE proposed geometries, but also current pavements, including the bright ones, LED sources, 3D objects detection (instead of 2D shapes as used in the past), and the concept of moving observer. SURFACE is going to do subjective tests using the virtual driving simulator of OPTIS-ANSYS: the r-tables of SURFACE data have been converted in the OPTIS file format and the SURFACE test set will be tested by virtual subjective experiments in the next. All these new additional aspects need to be tested: a full approach to road-lit environment, including observer (human or machine) is necessary to maximize the effects and to hit the target of EU Vision Zero – to reduce road deaths to almost zero by 2050. The research is just at its early stage with the SURFACE project, new funding will be necessary also to extend research and outcomes to Autonomous Driving.

5 REFERENCES

1. CIE 66-1984. *Road Surfaces and lighting*, joint CIE/PIARC publication, 1984, 71p.
2. CIE 140-2000. *Road Lighting Calculations*, Technical Report, 2000, 28p.
3. CIE 144-2001. *Road surface and road marking reflexion characteristics*, Technical Report, 2001, 42p.
4. EN 13201-3:2015. *Road lighting - Part 3: Calculation of performance*.
5. EN1436: 2018. *Road marking materials - Road marking performance for road users and test methods*.
6. Sorensen K, Obro P, Rasmussen B., *A review of the suitability of the average luminance coefficient Q_0 for road surfaces and road markings – and proposal for a different parameter*, Lys& Optik: note n°8, februar 1991.
7. Sorensen K., *Q_0 and Q_d – “lightness” of road surfaces in road lightning*, *Light and optics*, November 1992.
8. Nielsen H.O. and Obro P. *Mean luminance coefficient in diffuse illumination, Q_d for road surfaces and road markings – Laboratory tests*, Lys and optic, note n°21, April 1992.
9. Brusque C and Carta C., *Etude comparative des paramètres Q_0 et Q_d décrivant la clarté des revêtements routiers: typologie et modélisation des caractéristiques photométriques des matériaux*, LCPC report (subject n°261116), Januar 1997, in French.
10. Gibbons R., 1997, *Influence of Pavement Reflection on Target Visibility*, 1997, PhD study.
11. Chain C., Marchaut V., *R-tables for other observation angles: specific needs for two applications in the field of public lighting.*, CIE 2008
12. Fotios S, Uttley J, Cheal C, Hara N, *Using eye-tracking to identify pedestrians’ critical Visual tasks. Part 1. Dual task approach*. *Lighting Research and Technology*, 2015; 47:133–148.
13. Igari D, Shimizu M, Fukuda R., *Eye movements of elderly people while riding bicycles*. *Gerontechnology*, 2008; 7: 128.
14. Fotios S., Castleton H.F., *Lighting for cycling in the UK—A review*, LRT, Vol 49 n°3, 2017
15. Stockmar A, *Extension of the luminance concept of the luminance concept in road and tunnel lighting*, CIE2015
16. Sørensen K., Ekrias A., Hafdell P. & Corell D, *Reflection properties of road surfaces in Denmark*, 17 May 2017
17. Soardo P, Iacomussi P., Rossi G., Fellin L., *Compatibility of road lighting with star visibility*, *Lighting research Technology*, 40: 307-422, 2008.
18. Soardo P, Iacomussi P., Rossi G., *The luminance coefficient in road lighting. A parameter to save energy and reducing atmospheric pollution*, Proc. 11th Lux Europa Intl. Congress, Istanbul 9-11 September 2009
19. Waldrum J.M., 1972, *The calculation of sky haze luminance from street lighting*. *Lighting Research and Technology*. 4: 21-26
20. Crawford, David L. "Light pollution, radio interference, and space debris." IAU Colloq. 112: Light Pollution, Radio Interference, and Space Debris. Vol. 17. 1991.
21. Garstang, R. H. "Dust and light pollution." *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific* 103.668 (1991): 1109.
22. CIE150-2017, ***Guide on the Limitation of the Effects of Obtrusive Light from Outdoor Lighting Installations, 2nd Edition***, 48p, 2017
23. XP X90-13: 2011. *External light pollution - Control and calculation methods*
24. NF P98-351: 2010. *Characteristics, testing and rules for ground installation of pedotactile caution warning devices for blind or partially sighted persons*.

25. Greffier F, Muzet V, Boucher V, Fournela F, Dronneau. *Use of an imaging luminance measuring device to evaluate road lighting performance at different angles of observation*, Proceedings of XXIX CIE session in Washington DC, june 2019, <https://doi.org/10.25039/x46.2019.OP75>
26. [Waldrum J.M., 1972. The calculation of sky haze luminance from street lighting. *Lighting Research and Technology*. 4: 21-26](#)
27. First Stakeholder meeting presentation of the European EMPIR project <http://surface-nrm02.eu/> “16NRM02 Surface Pavement Surface Characterisation for Smart and Efficient Road Lighting”, Berlin 25 may 2018, <https://surface-nrm02.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/SURFACE-1st-stakeholder-meeting-small-1.pdf>
28. Gidlund, H., Lindgren, M., Muzet, V., Rossi, G. & Iacomussi, P. (2019) Road Surface Photometric Characterisation and Its Impact on Energy Savings. *Coatings journal* DOI: 10.3390/coatings9050286